

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES WITH LARGE REPEAT UNIT CELLS

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1 General Introduction

This paper presents in-plane shear, open-hole tension and mode 1 fracture toughness data for 3D woven angle interlock carbon fibre composites. The in-plane shear moduli of 3D woven angle interlock composites was measured using 4 different test methods. In previous work the in-plane shear modulus (G_{xy}) was determined via the plate twist test and the results compared with the G_{xy} determined via the V-notched beam Iosipescu (ASTM D5379) and V-notched rail shear (ASTM D7078) methods and the. In this paper the results are compared with measurements taken by tensile test of a $\pm 45^\circ$ 3D woven composite. Furthermore, open-hole tension tests and mode 1 fracture toughness tests were conducted on the 3D woven composite. The results indicate that both the plate twist and tensile test of a $\pm 45^\circ$ 3D woven composite methods are suitable for the measurement of in-plane shear modulus for different 3D weave architectures with large repeat unit cells and that the measurement is more representative of the global material response.

The open-hole tension results show that 3D woven composites are less notch-sensitive than laminated composites. A weave style was developed to manufacture Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens for testing and a significant increase in the Mode 1 fracture toughness Propagation, G_{IC} was observed.

2 Methods

Weaving technology is increasingly being used to produce dry multilayered preforms that are subsequently infused with a liquid matrix material to produce high performance composites. Three dimensionally (3D) woven composites, in particular, have been shown to possess many advantages compared to traditional performing methods with the

ability to tailor fiber placement in the X-, Y-, and Z-axis directions[1]. Manufacturing and performance advantages have been discussed extensively in literature, for example, improvements in compression-after-impact (CAI) strength compared with two-dimensional (2D) laminated composites and the ability to produce 'near-net-shape' preforms. Subsequently, various authors have developed a range of modeling tools, for example, to predict the geometry of the unit cell, elastic stiffness and failure strength.

Mechanical testing standards for FRP composites are not universally accepted and understood for 3D woven composites. Standard test methods however, are employed to 3D woven composites and some test standards are applicable. For instance uniaxial testing standards (BS and ASTM methods) for FRP composites have been used widely to determine the uniaxial strength and modulus of 3D woven composite materials.

It is apparent from the body of testing work that has been carried out on 3D woven composites, that it is of utmost importance that the sample dimensions encapsulate a representative portion of the actual weave architecture (unit cell). This becomes particularly important for determination of interlaminar shear performance. Weissenbach examined the issue of testing 3D woven composites with large unit cells and focused on the experimental and theoretical determination of interlaminar shear. Weissenbach reviewed a number of shear testing methods including short-beam-shear, Iosipescu, rail shear and off-axis tension. The suitability of the respective methods was critically assessed with regards to their ability to capture a representative response of the weave architecture in the 3D woven composite. The plate twist method was selected for the determination of the in-plane shear modulus. The

use of the plate twist method is attractive because it did not require the use of strain gauges. In addition, the global material response is represented with this test technique, which would indicate that it is more suitable for testing the materials discussed in this work (unit cell size approximately 30 by 50mm through the full thickness of the laminate). In a review paper by Tan et al. the authors reported from a numerical study by Whitney *et al.* on 3D woven angle interlock composite, who found the in-plane properties to be very sensitive to changes in FVF. Therefore, local measurements of shear properties using the standard test for in-plane shear measurement such as the V-notch Iosipescu may not be suitable for determining the shear modulus of 3D woven composites[30] considering that there are local variations in FVF across the repeat of the unit cell – for instance resin rich areas where the binder travels through the thickness.

Figure 1. Representation of the weave architecture of AI/02 and AI/03[2]

3 Results

The results indicate that both the plate twist and tensile test of a $\pm 45^\circ$ 3D woven composite methods are suitable for the measurement of in-plane shear modulus for different 3D weave architectures with large repeat unit cells and that the measurement is more representative of the global material response.

The open-hole tension results show that 3D woven composites are less notch-sensitive than laminated composites, and a significant increase in the Mode I fracture toughness Propagation, G_{IC} was observed.

Figure 2. Shear stress v shear strain on tensile Test of 3D Woven Carbon Fiber ± 45 Laminate

Figure 3. DCB test.

Figure 4. Open-hole tension results

References

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